

CRAFT-OA

Evaluation of Community Feedback from the 1st CRAFT-OA Summer School for Journal Editors in Telč (CZ) 2024

Discussion of Results with a Focus on the CRAFT-OA Institutional Publishing Technical Living Handbook

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Table of Contents

Abstract.....	2
Introduction.....	2
Frame	2
Contextualization and Goals.....	3
General Goal	4
Specific Goal Related to the Living Handbook (LH)	4
Methododology.....	5
The Approach: Surveys and Workshop	6
Pre-Summer School Survey.....	6
Mentimeter Surveys (Event-Specific Feedback)	6
Workshop on the Living Handbook.....	7
Post-Summer School Survey	7
Conclusion	7
Interpretation of all Results	7
Implications of All Results for the Living Handbook	8
Recommendations for the Living Handbook.....	8
Appendix.....	10
Results of Pre-Summer School Survey.....	10
Level of Experience	10
Interest in Areas of Publishing Focus.....	11
Usage of OJS and Other Systems	12
Usage of OJS and other Systems for Peer Review	13
Usage and Interest in XML Publishing	15
Needs for Information in Indexing and Databases	16

Needs for Information in Metadata Enhancement	18
Usage of Sources to Obtain Information and Support	19
Sufficiency of These Information Sources	20
Results from Mentimeter Polls.....	21
Topics of interest	21
Preferred Formats of Content.....	22
Results of the Workshop for Shaping the Living Handbook.....	23
Persona Ada (Platform Admin, Expert Level)	23
Persona Daria (Beginner, Non-Technical Staff)	23
Persona John (Advanced Editor, Scholar/Scientist).....	23
Persona Lucy (Beginner Editor, Academic).....	24
Implications for the Living Handbook.....	24
Results of Post-Summer School Survey.....	24
Organisational Affiliation.....	24
Usage of the learning material	25

Abstract

This paper shares community feedback from the first CRAFT-OA Summer School for Journal Editors in Telč (CZ) 2024, with a focus on the CRAFT-OA Institutional Publishing Technical Living Handbook. The program of the Summer School gave support to journal editors with the aim to improve their skills in applying Open Journal Systems (OJS) and offering Diamond Open Access (DOA) publication services. The feedback was gathered through surveys and Mentimeter polls. Results of the evaluation show high satisfaction and highlighting areas for improvement, such as XML publishing and accessibility. Based on these insights, recommendations were made to help develop the Living Handbook into a useful resource for the academic publishing community. The appendix contains evaluation and analysis of the data collected through the feedback.

Introduction

Frame

The EU-funded project CRAFT-OA aims to enhance the technical and organisational foundation for Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing. Diamond OA refers to a scholarly publication model where journals and platforms charge no fees to authors or readers, embodying principles of equity, community ownership, and bibliodiversity. This model supports a diverse range of small-scale, multilingual, and multicultural scholarly

communities, which make up 8-9% of the total article publication volume and 45% of Open Access publishing worldwide.¹ One key task of the CRAFT-OA project is to analyze the technical challenges faced by Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) and Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Providers (IPTPs), identifying gaps and proposing solutions. Complementarily, the DIAMAS project focuses on mapping the institutional publishing landscape in Europe to elevate academic publishing standards and address technical aspects of OA publishing.²

Additionally, the project aims to boost the visibility, recognition, and discoverability of Diamond OA publications, linking them to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other major data aggregators. The technical gap analysis identifies significant barriers, such as the insufficient application of technical standards and challenges related to publishing software like Open Journal Systems (OJS). The findings inform targeted measures, including training materials, toolkits, and recommendations, which are being developed to mitigate these issues.³

The Hamburg State and University Hamburg (SUB Hamburg) is one of 23 institutions from 14 European countries in the CRAFT-OA project. Within the project, SUB Hamburg is responsible for planning and realising the Institutional Publishing Technical Living Handbook. This handbook is a key resource designed to give ongoing support, share best practices, and provide guidance specifically for Diamond OA's publishing. Through its work, SUB Hamburg helps strengthen the technical foundations of Diamond OA and builds a valuable, lasting resource to help journal editors, platform providers, and the wider academic publishing community keep up with changing standards and technologies.

The need for ongoing professional development in academic publishing is especially important due to the rapid changes in digital technologies and OA models. This evaluation shows how focused training programs can improve the skills and knowledge of journal editors, raising the quality and sustainability of Diamond OA publishing. The Living Handbook is an essential tool in this fast-changing environment, helping to build a knowledgeable and collaborative community that can handle the challenges of modern academic publishing.

Contextualization and Goals

The CRAFT-OA 2024 Summer School for Journal Editors, held from May 27th to 31st at the Masaryk University Center in Telč, Czech Republic, was designed to enhance the skills of journal editors by offering targeted training and networking opportunities.⁴ The Summer School contributed to the broader goals outlined in the CRAFT-OA Grant Agreement, which

¹ Bosman, J., Frantsvåg, J. E., Kramer, B., Langlais, P.-C., & Proudman, V. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558704>.

² Varachkina, H., Umerle, T., Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., Šterbenc Svetina, B., Edig, X. van ., Fenner, J., Meinecke, I., Guignon, S., Stone, G., Souplet, J.-C., & Armengou, C. (2024). CRAFT-OA deliverable D2.3 "Technical gap analysis and high-level community transition plans" (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13235437>.

³ CRAFT-OA D2.3, Technical gap analysis, 2024.

⁴ CRAFT-OA (2024). Summer School 2024. Retrieved November 25, 2024, from <https://www.craft-oa.eu/summer-school-2004/>.

states that “user support will also supervise Diamond OA publishing infrastructure, practices, and uptake, providing specific insights into publishing efforts across different countries. A summer school will be organised to support the drafting of the handbook (hands-on validation in an early phase) as well as preparing the subsequent uptake of results (standards, practices, technologies) in a practical manner by the community.”⁵ In alignment with this directive, the project employs a robust Communication & Dissemination Plan (D7.1) to inform and engage stakeholders, ensure sustainability, and promote greater visibility for Diamond OA publishing. This plan outlines a multi-phase approach that includes launching activities, engaging stakeholders, disseminating results, and maintaining project outcomes beyond the funding period.⁶ Tailored specifically for editors proficient in Open Journal Systems (OJS), the first Summer School was organised by Muni Press, with a program committee composed of Masaryk University (MUNI), University of Göttingen (UGOE), the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA), and the SUB Hamburg.

The organisation of the Summer School was structured to ensure active engagement and feedback from participants. Two primary surveys were conducted—one before the program and one after it concluded. These surveys aimed to assess participants’ experiences, gauge their skill levels, and understand their expectations. Additionally, Mentimeter surveys were held after each of the five sessions to capture immediate reactions and insights, adding further depth to the overall evaluation.

General Goal

The overarching goal of this evaluation is to assess the effectiveness and impact of the Summer School program on the professional development of participating journal editors, with a particular emphasis on evaluating improvements in technical skills, editorial practices, and familiarity with Open Journal Systems (OJS)⁷ and Diamond OA publishing principles. By identifying both the strengths and areas for enhancement, this research aims to provide actionable insights that inform the development of future educational initiatives for journal editors. Additionally, the findings will support the integration of Summer School insights into the Living Handbook, ensuring that it serves as a comprehensive, up-to-date resource tailored to the evolving needs of editors in the academic publishing community.

Specific Goal Related to the Living Handbook (LH)

A key aspect of this evaluation is to determine how the knowledge and insights from the Summer School can be systematically integrated into the Living Handbook. Essential features and recommendations for the Living Handbook are identified and refined within this framework to guide the conceptualisation and technical selection, creating a robust tool that supports editors at all levels of knowledge and experience.

⁵ Grant Agreement, p. 13.

⁶ Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., Holsinger, S., Klaus, T., & Posavec, K. (2024). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan (Final). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13628430>.

⁷ Public Knowledge Project (PKP). (n.d.). *Open Journal Systems*. Retrieved November 25, 2024, from <https://pkp.sfu.ca/software/ojs/>.

Methododology

To evaluate the impact and effectiveness of the Summer School program, comprehensive mixed-methods approaches were implemented including multiple surveys, real-time feedback sessions, and a dedicated workshop focused on the Living Handbook. In particular, the workshop approach provided detailed insights into participants' experiences and skill development, supporting targeted recommendations for enhancing the Living Handbook.

Three key surveys were conducted to gather feedback on participants' professional backgrounds, learning outcomes, and expectations. The first, a pre-Summer School survey conducted about three weeks before the program, aimed to establish a baseline understanding of participants' editorial experience, familiarity with Open Journal Systems (OJS), and main challenges in publishing. It was completed by 50 participants. This baseline data helped identify areas where the Summer School could offer targeted support.

The organisation of the Summer School was structured to ensure active engagement and feedback from participants. With an average of 50 responses per session, totalling 250 responses, these surveys enabled participants to share their reactions to session content, identify areas of interest, and suggest topics for further exploration. The Mentimeter feedback highlighted key areas such as XML publishing, accessibility, and platform-specific knowledge, all of which were identified as crucial for future development.

Following the event, a post-Summer School survey was conducted to assess the impact on participants' skills and knowledge. Also completed by 50 participants, it included questions on perceived improvements in technical abilities, satisfaction with program content, and the effectiveness of different training formats. Comparing pre- and post-survey responses allowed to measure changes in participants' self-assessed skill levels and to identify successful aspects of the program.

In addition to these data aggregations, a dedicated workshop was held to get the community involved in the development of the Living Handbook. During this workshop, participants worked on creating personas representing typical users of the Handbook. These personas helped clarify the specific needs, goals, and challenges of different user groups. The creation of these personas allowed for a targeted content structure within the Handbook, aligning its design and functions to support each user group effectively. The personas informed decisions about content and navigation, ensuring that the Living Handbook provides relevant and valuable information for both beginners and experts. Insights from this workshop directly influenced the planning and conceptualisation of the Handbook, guiding the development of features and content that best serve its diverse audience.

The surveys and the workshop covered various topics relevant to participants' roles and responsibilities, including editorial experience, familiarity with technical standards such as XML and accessibility, and challenges in editorial workflows, including multilingualism and metadata management. They also explored the effectiveness of different training formats—such as presentations, workshops, and hands-on sessions—and participants' preferences for content formats within the Living Handbook, such as guidelines, checklists, and case studies. Mentimeter feedback and workshop results were particularly valuable for refining the

proposed structure of the Living Handbook, enabling the development of personas and organising content based on participant needs.

Survey data were analysed quantitatively to identify trends, with a focus on changes in self-assessed skill levels and participant satisfaction before and after the program. Responses from the Mentimeter surveys and the workshop were analysed to identify popular topics, central needs, and common areas of interest, which supported both the evaluation of the Summer School program and the design of the Living Handbook.

The community surveys involved 50 participants from diverse backgrounds, including academic institutions, libraries, and publishing houses. Many participants were affiliated with Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) and Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Providers (IPTPs), representing a broad range of editorial experience and technical skills. This survey- and workshop-based research design enabled a multi-dimensional evaluation of the Summer School program's impact. The results served as the foundation for targeted recommendations for the Living Handbook, ensuring that it effectively addresses the diverse needs of journal editors in the academic publishing sector.

The Approach: Surveys and Workshop

To evaluate the Summer School program's effectiveness and gather comprehensive feedback from participants, we conducted two primary surveys—one administered before the program and one following its completion. These surveys were designed to assess participants' experiences, gauge their skill levels, and understand their expectations.⁸ Additionally, Mentimeter surveys were conducted after each event to capture immediate reactions and insights, providing further depth to our evaluation.

Pre-Summer School Survey

The pre-Summer School survey aimed to establish a baseline of participants' editorial experience, familiarity with Open Journal Systems (OJS), and primary publishing focuses. Participants were asked to provide information about their professional backgrounds, including the volume of submissions they typically manage, the structure of their editorial teams, and the specific journal management tools they use. Additional questions addressed challenges faced in areas such as multilingual publishing, accessibility, metadata enhancement, and XML usage. This initial survey helped understand the range of expertise among participants and identified key areas where support was most needed.

Mentimeter Surveys (Event-Specific Feedback)

Mentimeter surveys were conducted at the end of each event within the Summer School to capture immediate, event-specific feedback. These surveys allowed participants to share their reactions to the material covered, identify topics of interest, and suggest areas for

⁸ Miller, T. I., Kobayashi, M. M., Caldwell, E., Thurston, S., & Collett, B. (2002). Citizen Surveys on the Web: General Population Surveys of Community Opinion. *Social Science Computer Review*, 20(2), 124-136. <https://doi.org/10.1177/089443930202000203>.

further exploration. Mentimeter feedback also helped highlight trends in participants' interests, with XML publishing, accessibility, and platform-specific knowledge emerging as frequently cited topics of importance. By collecting this real-time feedback, a nuanced understanding of participants' immediate learning needs and preferences was gained.

Workshop on the Living Handbook

In addition to the surveys, a workshop was held to work on the Living Handbook concept. During this workshop, participants helped create "personas" representing typical users of the Handbook, such as beginner editors, advanced editors, platform administrators, and non-technical staff. These personas allowed to understand the unique needs, goals, and challenges faced by different user groups, helping to design the Handbook to serve a wide range of users effectively. The insights from this workshop directly shaped the content structure and navigation of the Living Handbook, ensuring it would be a valuable tool for users at all levels of experience.

Together, the surveys and workshop provided multi-layered insights into participants' needs, helping develop targeted recommendations for the Living Handbook and assess the Summer School's success in enhancing skills within the academic publishing community.

Post-Summer School Survey

The post-Summer School survey sought to measure the impact of the program by comparing participants' self-reported skill levels and knowledge with those indicated in the pre-survey. This survey included questions about participants' satisfaction with the program, perceived skill improvement, and the relevance of the topics covered. Participants were also asked to reflect on the effectiveness of different training formats used during the program, such as presentations, workshops, and discussions. This feedback provided insights into which formats were most conducive to learning and engagement for journal editors.

Conclusion

Interpretation of all Results

The findings from the surveys, Mentimeter feedback, and the workshop highlight that the Summer School program effectively addresses the training needs of journal editors. It provides participants with the essential skills and knowledge required to navigate the evolving landscape of modern academic publishing. The emphasis on XML publishing and accessibility, identified as critical areas during the program, underscores the necessity for specialised training to equip editors with the ability to manage digital content effectively and ensure it is accessible to a diverse audience. These topics are increasingly relevant as publishing shifts towards more digital formats, making it crucial for editors to stay updated with the latest standards and technologies.

The strong preference expressed by participants for interactive training formats, such as presentations, workshops, and discussions, indicates that future training programs should continue to incorporate a variety of engaging, hands-on learning experiences. These formats

allow participants to directly apply what they learn in practical scenarios, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the training. The preference for structured learning formats like guidelines and training materials, as seen in the Mentimeter surveys, suggests that journal editors value clear, detailed instructions and resources they can refer back to as needed.

Implications of All Results for the Living Handbook

The insights gathered from this evaluation have significant implications for the development of the Living Handbook. While its primary aim is to support journal editors and technical staff within the Diamond OA community, the Handbook also contributes to broader efforts to foster global collaboration and alignment among Diamond OA initiatives. The concept of a Global Diamond Federation (GDF), as proposed by Pierre Mounier and Johan Rooryck, highlights the necessity of federating diverse initiatives under shared principles and goals. By drawing on established infrastructures and long-standing contributors to Diamond OA, such as the Public Knowledge Project (PKP), the GDF aims to provide resources and services that strengthen the role of Diamond OA in scholarly communication. The Living Handbook aligns with this vision by serving as a resource for knowledge sharing and capacity building.⁹

Recommendations for the Living Handbook

Based on insights from the Summer School program, Mentimeter surveys, and workshop findings, the following recommendations are proposed for the Living Handbook. These suggestions outline the essential functions and priorities that should be integrated to ensure the Handbook becomes a valuable and effective tool for its users.

First, it is recommended to provide content on XML publishing. This should include guides for XML publishing, with troubleshooting sections to help users solve common issues. Additionally, it is recommended to provide regular updates to keep users informed about current standards and technological advancements. Ensuring that the content should be available to users of all experience levels, from beginners to advanced practitioners.

Next, it is recommended to implement navigation and content organization based on user roles. A user-friendly interface should allow users to select their user type on entry, so the Handbook can filter content and display the most relevant resources based on the user's role and experience level. For instance, introductory guides would be prioritised for beginners (like "Daria" and "Lucy"), while more advanced, detailed guides would be accessible to experts (like "Ada"). Content creation and updates should be aligned with each user type's specific needs.

Simplicity and accessibility are crucial elements. The Handbook should use clear, easy-to-understand language, especially in sections intended for beginners. Intuitive navigation features should make it easy for users to find resources, while visual aids can enhance understanding. To further improve usability, enhancing the search function with basic user type integration is also recommended. A simple search system should allow users to filter

⁹ Willinsky, J. & Alperin, J. P. (February 25, 2024). The Platform Developers in a Federated Model of Diamond Open Access. *the diamond papers*. Retrieved November 25, 2024, from <https://doi.org/10.58079/12712>.

results based on their user role, helping them quickly access relevant content. It is essential to create an intuitive and efficient search experience, with regular updates to the search index and potentially integrating user feedback to continuously improve search relevance and ease of use.

The handbook should also include practical, structured learning resources such as guides, training materials, case studies, and possibly checklists. These resources should be well-organized and easy to navigate, providing both detailed articles and brief checklists for quick reference. Regular updates and expansions of these resources could ensure that new topics in academic publishing are covered and that different learning preferences are addressed.

Appendix

Results of Pre-Summer School Survey

Level of Experience

The evaluation of editors based on experience levels reveals a diverse range of expertise within the group. Editors with extensive experience are deeply involved in editorial processes and demonstrate their long-term commitment. Those with moderate experience show solid competence in their roles, though not reaching expert level. Editors with limited experience are still in the process of learning and developing their skills.

The data indicates that the majority of respondents are classified as advanced editors, reflecting a solid foundation of editorial knowledge. At the same time, the presence of beginner editors highlights the potential for ongoing professional development. The smaller, yet significant, group of expert editors represents a valuable resource of deep expertise within the community.

Given the limited number of experts, advanced editors have the opportunity to deepen their knowledge and progress into expert roles. This pathway enables structured development, allowing advanced editors to gradually take on more responsibility. Beginner editors could benefit from targeted training initiatives that offer valuable learning experiences and accelerate their growth. Such training could empower beginners to handle more complex tasks and make a stronger contribution to the editorial process. This structure of continued development supports both individual growth and the collective strength of the community.

Interest in Areas of Publishing Focus

Thirteen editors prioritised technical aspects, while twelve maintained a balanced focus, indicating the importance of both technical skills and editorial content management. The slightly higher number of editors focusing on technical aspects indicates a notable emphasis on technology within the publishing process.

The increasing importance of technical competencies in publishing underscores that the Living Handbook must make comprehensive technical knowledge accessible to its users. As a central platform, it should offer practical guidance and technical training that enables publishers and editors to efficiently use digital tools and platforms. The range of topics should span from fundamental aspects, such as utilizing OJS platforms, to more advanced technologies. Integrating such content would help users meet the growing technical demands while simultaneously optimising the digitisation of their workflows.

Moreover, the nearly equal representation of editors with a balanced focus indicates a rising need for a mix of both technical and editorial expertise. The Living Handbook should support this need for versatility by providing content that encourages editors and publishers to transition smoothly between editorial and technical work. This means the Living Handbook must offer not only technical training but also approaches for editorial work in a digital environment. In this way, editors and publishers could develop the essential skills needed to successfully integrate both areas.

Usage of OJS and Other Systems

A significant number of editors fall into the category of experienced OJS users, having worked with the platform for several years. This extensive experience shows that they are well-versed not only in editorial processes but also in the technical aspects of OJS, such as installation, configuration, and customisation. Many of these editors manage these technical elements themselves, demonstrating a deep understanding of the system's functions and requirements. Their expertise allows them to efficiently resolve technical issues, implement updates, and tailor features to meet the specific needs of their journals. Additionally, they often support less experienced team members, helping to ensure that editorial workflows run smoothly. Despite the many participants with extensive OJS experience, there remains a significant need for training within the community. This highlights the diversity of the user base and the varying levels of experience with journal management systems. Less experienced editors or those new to OJS often require assistance with basic functions, workflow management, and technical troubleshooting. The diversity in experience levels creates an environment where structured training can play a central role.

For the Living Handbook, a dual approach to content and resource development would be beneficial. On the one hand, it should offer advanced documentation, troubleshooting guides, and case studies on technical optimisation to support experienced editors. On the other, it should provide foundational training materials, beginner guides, and interactive resources to help new users get started with OJS and build confidence and skills.

This dual approach would ensure that the Living Handbook remains relevant and useful for all members of the OJS community, reinforcing its role as a comprehensive resource for managing Open Access journals. The responses to this question indicate that, for most editors, OJS is the primary or even sole platform for managing journal workflows. The predominant use of OJS highlights its central role as the main system these editors rely on, with only a few respondents having experience with alternative systems. This strong reliance

on OJS shapes their approach to handling submissions, peer-review processes, and publication workflows.

For many, experience in journal management is highly specialised and focused on OJS-related tasks. Those with knowledge of other journal management systems often have targeted, specialised expertise—usually limited to specific roles or functions within the publication workflow. Some users, for example, have developed expertise in peer review processes, while others focus on managing particular segments of the workflow, such as submission tracking or publication scheduling. This specialised experience underscores how OJS has become a central tool for these editors, helping them build deep, although sometimes narrowly focused, competencies within the system.

This specialisation also means that there is limited cross-platform experience among OJS users, which may result in some editors missing opportunities to learn from the features of other systems. For the Living Handbook, this suggests that it would be beneficial to cater to a user base that relies heavily on OJS and could benefit from comprehensive, OJS-specific resources. At the same time, introducing comparative insights or best practices from other platforms could broaden users’ perspectives, helping them optimise their use of OJS by drawing from the strengths of other systems.

In this context, the Living Handbook could serve as both a foundational and advanced resource. For new users, it could provide step-by-step guides on the basic functions of OJS, helping them feel confident navigating the system. For more experienced users, it could offer deeper insights into workflow customisation, plugin integration, and advanced technical troubleshooting, catering to their specialised needs. By providing both types of resources, the Living Handbook can expand users’ expertise and foster a strong, well-informed community around OJS, equipping editors to manage their journal workflows effectively and confidently.

Usage of OJS and other Systems for Peer Review

Many journals are already using OJS or other systems to manage the peer review process, emphasising the essential role these tools play in organising and optimising peer review. The reliance on systems like OJS shows that technological support has become an integral component for many journals to ensure a well-organized peer review workflow.

At the same time, there is a considerable number of respondents who currently do not use journal management systems for peer review. This highlights several potential areas for growth and development. For journals that have not yet adopted these tools, there may be barriers to implementation, such as lack of familiarity with the systems, concerns about setup costs, or uncertainties about the benefits. Alternatively, it may point to a need for targeted support in integrating these systems effectively into existing workflows. By providing specific training, case studies, or demonstrations that show how OJS can simplify peer review, more journals could be encouraged to transition to digital systems, thereby enhancing their efficiency and transparency. Furthermore, responses suggest that some journals are planning to adopt OJS or similar systems for peer review in the near future. This anticipated growth indicates a positive trend towards the broader use of technological solutions in editorial management. For the Living Handbook, this increase in adoption presents an opportunity to provide targeted resources to support journals as they begin to use OJS. By offering resources specifically for peer review, the Handbook could play a crucial role in assisting journals with this transition.

In this context, the Living Handbook could play a key role in supporting both current and future OJS users in peer review management. For experienced users, it could offer advanced insights into optimising and customising the peer review process within OJS, such as setting up automated workflows and integrating additional plugins. For new or prospective users, it could provide essential resources on setting up peer review in OJS and overcoming initial challenges. By supporting journals at different stages of technological adoption, the Living Handbook could help foster a broader transition to digital tools in peer review. This support could contribute to a general improvement in peer review standards within the Open Access community.

Usage and Interest in XML Publishing

The data shows that XML publishing is not yet widespread among respondents; the majority indicate that they are currently not using XML in their journal workflows. This limited adoption may be due to a lack of awareness of XML’s benefits or the perceived complexity involved in establishing XML-based workflows. For many, the technical requirements of XML—such as structuring content with XML tags and integrating XML into existing systems—appear challenging, especially without prior experience or technical support.

However, there is a notable and growing interest in XML publishing. Several respondents have expressed a desire to learn more about XML or plan to integrate it into their workflows in the future. This growing interest may be attributed to an increasing awareness of XML’s advantages, such as improved content structure, flexibility, and reusability. XML enables precise formatting and tagging of article content, which can be particularly advantageous for indexing, accessibility, and multi-format publishing. As journals look for ways to make their content more accessible, adaptable, and searchable, XML may become a more appealing option for a broader range of publications.

Those currently using XML often work with highly specialised workflows that require specific tools and plugins. Some users have integrated tools like the JATS Parser Plugin or work with XML-TEI files, both of which support highly structured and detailed tagging systems for journal articles. The use of these tools indicates a targeted approach to XML publishing, where users leverage XML’s capabilities for specific purposes, such as enhancing interoperability with databases or enabling seamless integration with digital libraries. These users demonstrate a deeper understanding of XML’s potential to increase the precision and flexibility of digital publishing and could be valuable resources within the community for others considering XML adoption.

This context offers several opportunities for the Living Handbook. First, it could provide foundational educational resources to make XML more accessible to those unfamiliar with it. Introductory guides explaining the benefits of XML and the basic principles of structuring content in XML format would be helpful. Tutorials on using XML tools like the JATS Parser Plugin or creating XML-TEI files could also lower the entry barriers for new users. By breaking down complex XML workflows into manageable steps, the Handbook could make XML publishing accessible to a wider audience.

For those already using XML, the Living Handbook could offer advanced resources that delve deeper into the intricacies of XML publishing. These could include troubleshooting guides for common XML integration issues. Additionally, the Handbook could provide information on how XML enhances compatibility with other digital tools and platforms, such as repositories, archiving systems, and digital libraries. This information would be especially valuable for users looking to optimise and expand their XML-based publishing processes.

Supporting XML adoption and providing resources tailored to varying experience levels can foster greater familiarity with XML publishing within the academic community. The Living Handbook's support in this area could help journals transition smoothly to XML-based workflows, ultimately enhancing the quality, accessibility, and longevity of their published content.

Needs for Information in Indexing and Databases

A significant portion of respondents are focused on understanding detailed indexing procedures, such as how to apply them to specific databases, manage conference proceedings, and ensure proper indexing. This indicates a strong interest in practical, actionable information that can directly improve the indexing status of their journals. Many editors are keen to learn how to enhance the visibility and discoverability of their content through professional indexing.

The responses also reveal a broad range of informational needs, from specific indexing questions to general knowledge and best practices. This diversity in informational needs highlights that, alongside advanced topics related to database integration, there is also a demand for foundational knowledge to help editors understand indexing and confidently take the first steps. A tailored knowledge offering could assist users with different levels of experience, addressing their unique questions and guiding them effectively.

This presents numerous opportunities for training and resources aimed at supporting editors in navigating indexing and database processes. For example, training modules could be developed to explain the entire indexing process—from basic steps and prerequisites to the specific requirements of individual databases. This practical support could enable editors to better assess the necessary actions to make their journals visible in relevant academic databases and successfully achieve indexing.

Another important topic is the interest in workflow automation. This demand underscores the desire for increased efficiency and the potential for technology to streamline and accelerate indexing processes. Automated workflows could assist editors by optimising routine tasks such as metadata assignment or maintaining indexing data, thereby reducing manual workload and minimising errors. Implementing such automation technologies would enable journals to use their resources more efficiently and focus more on content-driven aspects.

In this context, the Living Handbook could play a central role by providing comprehensive resources on indexing procedures and practices. Foundational modules could cover the essential steps to prepare for and carry out indexing, while advanced content could address the specific requirements of individual databases or the automation of certain steps. A specially developed training program covering both basic knowledge and specialised topics could help target audiences index their journals strategically and efficiently, thereby sustainably enhancing content discoverability. The Living Handbook could also establish a dedicated section on automation, showcasing the best tools and methods for automating indexing processes.

Needs for Information in Metadata Enhancement

A significant portion of respondents show a strong interest in improving metadata, focusing on enhancing overall quality, visibility, and strategies for better metadata management. This growing interest suggests an increasing recognition of the importance of metadata in boosting journal discoverability and highlights metadata’s key role in making content accessible and visible in digital environments.

This presents a clear opportunity to provide targeted training and resources to support editors in developing effective metadata strategies. Training modules or resources could cover foundational topics, such as the importance of consistent metadata standards, along with advanced strategies for SEO optimisation and managing multilingual metadata. By equipping editors with practical tools and knowledge, these resources could empower them to implement metadata improvements that are crucial for expanding their reach and strengthening reader engagement.

The interest in best practices and standards also underscores the need for clear guidance in metadata management. Many editors may be looking for standardised approaches that align with industry best practices to ensure that their metadata not only meets quality standards but is also compatible with digital libraries, indexing services, and search engines.

In this context, the Living Handbook could include examples of successful metadata strategies from established journals. A dedicated section on multilingual metadata would be

particularly valuable, helping editors optimise metadata effectively across different platforms and languages.

Usage of Sources to Obtain Information and Support

Many respondents rely heavily on PKP resources, including the OJS forums, official documentation, and related websites, as their primary sources of information for scholarly publishing. This indicates that PKP resources are widely used and trusted within the community. However, there is also a risk of over-reliance on these resources. While PKP and OJS materials provide essential and helpful guidance, some respondents have raised concerns about the depth and user-friendliness of these resources.

This reliance on PKP resources highlights potential gaps in their comprehensiveness and accessibility. For editors who need specialised information tailored to individual workflows or advanced customisations, the existing PKP and OJS resources often fall short. This suggests that editors would benefit from expanded and more in-depth content that addresses complex requirements.

In addition to PKP resources, institutional support and internal resources play a crucial role in providing publishing-related information. Many editors benefit from local support, such as institution-specific documentation, IT support, and training, which complement the PKP resources and provide practical, context-specific insights. Such internal resources are often essential for the effective implementation and management of journal workflows. The findings also reveal a clear need for more comprehensive and accessible information sources, particularly for those who find the current PKP resources insufficient. Editors are looking for resources that cover both fundamental and advanced topics, making it easier for users with varying levels of experience to quickly find relevant information. In this context,

the Living Handbook could serve as a valuable resource by offering additional depth and more comprehensive content.

Sufficiency of These Information Sources

The varied assessments from respondents regarding existing PKP resources and institutional support point to important implications for the Living Handbook as a complementary resource. On one hand, many editors find PKP resources helpful, while others perceive gaps in their comprehensiveness and user-friendliness. Here, the Living Handbook could serve as an additional, more extensive resource by providing detailed and clearly structured guidelines, including ones for advanced topics. For example, it could offer accessible and easily navigable instructions for version updates and specific OJS customisations, thereby complementing existing PKP resources in a targeted way.

A common criticism of PKP resources is the challenging navigation. The Living Handbook could address this gap by offering a more user-friendly structure and navigation. This would enable users to more easily access relevant information and apply it directly to their specific needs. Moreover, the mixed perceptions of institutional support, such as local seminars, suggest that some editors need more structured training and targeted development opportunities. The Living Handbook could address this by offering training modules and guides that cover both fundamental and advanced topics, giving editors a solid foundation for effectively using OJS and optimising metadata management.

The demand for more comprehensive and practice-oriented information also suggests that editors value best practices and concrete use cases. The Living Handbook could provide case studies and examples of successful implementations, giving users practical insights into proven strategies and solutions, thus facilitating the transition from theory to practice. Since external professional networks are generally considered helpful, the Living Handbook could serve to complement these networks by organising and making their knowledge long-term

accessible. As a central point of contact for frequently asked questions and technical guidance, the Handbook could compile information from these networks and offer editors a reliable reference. In summary, the Living Handbook could effectively complement existing PKP and institutional resources as a comprehensive and practice-oriented resource

Results from Mentimeter Polls

After each event, targeted Mentimeter polls were conducted to gather valuable feedback from participants. These surveys aimed to better understand both the thematic interests of participants and their preferred formats for each topic. The results helped identify which content was in highest demand and in what format (e.g., guidelines, training materials, or articles) the information could be most effectively delivered. Through this continuous feedback loop, the content and formats in the Living Handbook could be tailored to meet the specific needs of the target audience. The polls also allowed for a flexible response to emerging interests or changing preferences.

Topics of interest

The extensive feedback indicates that the "Other Comments" category captured a wide range of additional topics not fully addressed by the predefined categories. This points to a broad spectrum of further concerns and suggestions. The XML, Publishing Platforms, and Standards/Policies categories also received significant attention, indicating key areas of interest or concern among respondents. In terms of areas to improve, the lower comment count in the Sources/Formats category suggests fewer concerns or issues in this area. The moderate number of comments on Knowledge Level, Metadata, and PDF still highlights their importance, though these topics seem less critical than the primary categories.

For the Living Handbook (LH), this analysis of feedback indicates that content and priorities should be aligned with users’ interests and needs. A focus on XML, publishing platforms, and standards/policies is essential, as the high level of interest in these topics signals a core demand. These areas should be addressed more comprehensively within the LH, possibly through in-depth chapters, guides, or best practices. Supplementary workshops or additional resources could further enhance users’ knowledge and skills in these key areas. In addition, flexibility and adaptability are crucial for the LH. The Handbook should be structured to respond quickly to emerging topics or changing needs. Regular feedback and surveys can help dynamically adjust priorities, ensuring the Handbook remains consistently relevant to its users.

Preferred Formats of Content

The analysis of respondents’ preferences for content formats shows clear trends in the types of resources they favour, divided into topic areas such as Challenges and Standards, Case Studies, Publishing Technology, and Training. The most popular formats are Guidelines and Training Materials in the areas of Publishing Technology and Training, with Guidelines receiving nine mentions and Training Materials eight. In the Training area specifically, Training Materials were the top choice with nine mentions, followed closely by Guidelines with eight. Less preferred formats include videos, which show the lowest preference across all categories, and checklists, which are moderately favoured but receive less interest than Guidelines and Training Materials. Overall, respondents demonstrate a strong preference for Guidelines and Training Materials across all content categories. In addition, articles are particularly sought after in the areas of Publishing Technology and Challenges and Standards.

For the formats offered in the Living Handbook (LH), this analysis indicates that the focus should be on guidelines and training materials, as these are the most preferred by users. These formats are especially valued in areas like publishing technology and training,

suggesting that practical guides and training resources are the most effective ways to meet users' needs. Articles could also play an important role, particularly in the areas of challenges and standards and publishing technology, where they show consistent demand. The LH should therefore include well-structured articles to provide in-depth insights and background knowledge on these specific topics. Less preferred formats, such as videos and checklists, could be offered optionally but should not be prioritised, given their lower demand. Instead, the LH should place a clear emphasis on the highly rated formats, providing users with a focused and user-friendly knowledge resource aligned with their preferences.

Results of the Workshop for Shaping the Living Handbook

The workshop conducted to shape the Living Handbook provided valuable insights into the needs of potential users. The workshop focused on the development of personas. These personas represent typical users, each with specific requirements, goals, and challenges, and are crucial for ensuring that the content and features of the Living Handbook are well-aligned with the target audience.

The workshop content was influenced by prior surveys conducted with potential users, which collected detailed feedback on their expectations and preferences. By combining survey results with discussions held during the workshop, the team was able to define these user groups and gain a deeper understanding of their daily workflows, knowledge levels, and common challenges. This approach ensures that the Living Handbook effectively addresses the practical needs of its users. Each persona, developed from workshop findings, now serves as a foundational guide for organising content, designing navigation, and selecting features.

Persona Ada (Platform Admin, Expert Level)

Ada's needs highlight the importance of providing detailed technical information, standards, and tools within the Handbook. As an expert with a strong IT background, Ada requires a reliable source of reference to support her work and community. The Handbook should include advanced technical documentation and up-to-date information on best practices and technical solutions.

Persona Daria (Beginner, Non-Technical Staff)

Daria, a project member with limited technical experience, requires basic information that is easy to understand. Her needs emphasise the importance of including beginner-friendly content, such as step-by-step guides on setting up new IPSP systems and finding support resources. The Living Handbook should cater to her needs with clear, accessible content designed for users new to the field.

Persona John (Advanced Editor, Scholar/Scientist)

John, an advanced editor, seeks comprehensive information on digital object architecture (DOA) and related topics. He values detailed training materials and community engagement.

The Living Handbook should serve as a thorough reference tool that is regularly updated by community contributions, providing John with the latest insights and developments.

Persona Lucy (Beginner Editor, Academic)

Lucy, a beginner editor, needs information on best practices, technical support, and platform decisions. Her priorities include finding grants and identifying IT staff for technical support. The Living Handbook should offer practical guides, checklists, and decision-making

Implications for the Living Handbook

The Living Handbook is designed to meet the specific needs of diverse user groups. A persona-based content organisation will be developed to ensure that content aligns with the roles and knowledge levels of its users. This approach makes it easier for users to quickly and efficiently find relevant information tailored precisely to their needs. Simplicity and accessibility are prioritised. Analysis shows that the Handbook must be clear and user-friendly, especially for beginners like Daria and Lucy. For this group, straightforward language and intuitive navigation are essential to help them easily find their way around the Handbook and access the information they need without difficulty. For advanced users like Ada, the Living Handbook has to provide comprehensive technical content and in-depth guidelines on standards and tools. This allows experienced users to rely on the Living Handbook as a trusted source of detailed technical information. To keep the Living Handbook relevant and up-to-date, continuous content updates are essential.

Results of Post-Summer School Survey

Organisational Affiliation

The data reveals that the majority of participants in the Summer School are affiliated with libraries and publishers, making up 37.5% and 25% of attendees, respectively. This suggests that library professionals are key stakeholders, likely due to their central role in journal management and open access initiatives, while publishers also show strong engagement,

reflecting their critical role in the journal ecosystem. Research-performing organisations, representing 18.8% of participants, indicate the involvement of researchers and institutions actively engaged in scholarly output. A smaller portion, 6.3%, comes from research infrastructure, showing limited but present interest from those supporting research frameworks. An additional 12.5% of participants fall into the "Other" category, covering a diverse range of affiliations beyond the predefined groups. Notably, there were no participants from research funding organisations, press & media, private commercial organisations, or private non-profit organisations, pointing to underrepresented or unrepresented groups. This distribution highlights the primary stakeholders in the Summer School and suggests potential areas for future outreach to engage these absent groups.

For the Living Handbook (LH), this distribution indicates that content and resources should be tailored to the needs of the primary target groups—namely, library professionals, publishers, and research-performing organisations. Since these groups make up the majority of Summer School participants, it is essential to offer practical, targeted content that aligns with their specific requirements.

Usage of the learning material

What kind of learning materials do you find most useful or would you find most useful as a journal editor/manager?

16 Antworten

The feedback from participants reveals clear preferences for various learning formats. A handbook based on text and images was the most preferred format, chosen by 37.5% of participants, indicating that traditional handbooks are especially effective for many editors in acquiring and retaining knowledge. A combination of handbooks and webinars was also favoured by 25% of participants, suggesting that a mix of written materials with interactive or visual elements can enrich the learning experience. Webinars (video recordings) and a journal editors' forum were each preferred by 12.5% of participants, showing that while these formats are less popular than handbooks, they still hold value for a certain group of learners.

Interestingly, no participants selected podcasts or collaborative tools like Wiki or Gitbook, suggesting that these formats may not align as well with the learning styles or needs of journal editors. The results show a strong preference for handbooks based on text and images, with 37.5% of participants finding them particularly useful. Additionally, 25% prefer

a combination of handbooks and webinars, highlighting the importance of varied learning formats. Webinars and editors' forums are also appreciated by a smaller group (12.5% each). The lack of interest in podcasts and collaborative tools suggests these formats are less relevant to this audience. These insights can guide the development of future learning materials to better meet the needs of journal editors and managers.

A Living Handbook offers many advantages and can be especially valuable in dynamic fields. Continuous updates keep it relevant, and regular user feedback allows content to be flexibly adapted to the needs of the target audience. Integrating various formats such as guidelines, and articles addresses different learning preferences and enhances knowledge transfer.